

EVALUATION OF BROILER AND SHEEP MEAT FOR BACTERIAL CONTAMINATION SOLD BY LOCAL VENDORS OF DISTRICT, HYDERABAD

Shafique Ahmed Koondhar^{*1}, Shahid Hussain Abro², Habibullah Janyaro³, Ghulam Mustafa Solangi⁴, Rehmat Ullah⁵, Piao Khan⁶, Imran Ahmed⁷, Anam Bashir⁸, Mudasar Ahmed Khosa⁹, Syed Shafat Ul Hassan Gilani¹⁰, Zafar Alam Jattak¹¹, Sakhi Bakhsh¹², Saeed Ahmed¹³

^{*1,2}Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam

³Department of Veterinary Surgery, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Sakrand

⁴Department of Veterinary Pathology, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Saranda

⁵Department of Clinical Medicine and Surgery, University of Agriculture Faisalabad

^{6, 8,9,11,12,13}Livestock and Dairy Development Department, Quetta, Baluchistan

⁶Department of Epidemiology and Public Health, University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore

^{7,10}Department of Livestock and Poultry Production, University of Poonch Rawalakot

^{*1}drshafiqueahmed231@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15735176>

Keywords

Broiler, Sheep, meat, Bacterial contamination, Local vendor, Hyderabad.

Article History

Received on 17 May 2025

Accepted on 17 June 2025

Published on 25 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Shafique Ahmed Koondhar

Abstract

Ensuring the availability of safe and wholesome food is essential for public health. However, raw meat can harbor harmful microbes leading to spoilage and foodborne illnesses. This study aimed to assess the bacterial contamination of broiler meat and sheep mutton sold by local vendors in Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan. A total of 100 samples—50 broilers and 50 mutton—were collected from five regions: Hirabad, Latif Abad, Phuleli, Qasim Abad, and Saddar. Samples were analyzed at the Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam, and the Central Veterinary Diagnostic Laboratory Tandojam. Bacterial species were identified through culture and biochemical tests, and antibiotic susceptibility was evaluated. Out of 100 samples, 25 (25%) were contaminated, with a higher prevalence in mutton (36%) compared to broiler meat (14%). Phuleli showed the highest contamination rates in both meat types. Bacterial load in broiler and mutton samples was 1.62×10^6 and 1.25×10^6 CFU/g, respectively. Bacteria isolated from broiler meat included *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Mutton samples yielded *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Campylobacter jejuni*. Antibiotic sensitivity testing revealed high effectiveness of ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, enrofloxacin, and erythromycin. Specifically, *E. coli* and *S. aureus* showed high sensitivity to ciprofloxacin and chloramphenicol, respectively. The study concludes that mutton is more contaminated than broiler meat and highlights the need for strict hygiene practices and effective antibiotic use to ensure food safety.

INTRODUCTION

Meat and its products are considered to be the most important part of balanced and nutritious diet. The meat has very high value of proteins, vitamins and minerals that are necessary for growth, repair and maintenance of body cells as well as for everyday activities of life (Kumbhar et al., 2018). The certain proteins, minerals and vitamins such as Vitamin-A and Vitamin-B12 present in raw meat could not be substituted by plant sources. Due to rich contents, it offers a highly favorable environment for growth of microbes. However the microbes present in raw meat can cause spoilage of meat and food borne diseases in humans as a consequence of socio-economic and health losses (Buriro et al., 2017). The animals that are usually slaughtered for meat purposes are sheep (Lamb- between 4-12 months of age and Mutton-greater than one year), cattle (Veal- 6-7months of age and Beef - 1 year of age), pig (pork), horse (horsemeat), goat (chevron) and fowl, largely chickens, turkeys and ducks, for poultry meat (USDA, 2000). At present broiler meat is one of the cheapest source and easily available in the market places. Broiler meat is easily digested and accepted by the most persons of society (Yashoda et al., 2001). Whereas, mutton meat is considered as an excellent source of food but it is more expensive than broiler meat. There are thirty local breeds of sheep in Pakistan. Lohi sheep breed is one of the most important and biggest breed used for mutton in the country (Saleem et al., 2015). Now a days, the contamination of raw meat by pathogens is one of the major challenge for the meat industry. Approximately 75% of pathogens affecting humans acquired from animals and animal origin products since last decades (WHO, 2011). The most common bacterial species found in meat are *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella*, *Aeromonas* spp, *Arobacter* spp and *Clostridium helicobacter* species. The most of people who consume raw meat where animals are slaughtered and sold in local shops, where the hygienic conditions of raw meat are always questionable. Hyderabad is the 5th largest city in Pakistan and second largest city of Sindh province. According to the 2012 survey of Pakistan, the Hyderabad had a population of 4.5 million, out of which 60.07% were live areas, making it second-

most urbanized district of Sindh after Karachi. As regards to bacterial contamination of broiler meat and sheep mutton, very few studies have been carried-out in Pakistan, but no such type of investigation has been made before in the Hyderabad, Sindh province. In this study therefore, it was planned to identify the bacteria in broiler meat and sheep mutton obtained from various regions of the Hyderabad. Further that the present investigation regarding meat will provide baseline knowledge about the contaminated meat sold in various regions of the Hyderabad. The present study will be also help in the recognition of bacterial species that are responsible for spoilage of meat.

Material and Methods:

Sample collection: A total of 100 raw meat samples, 50 from each broiler and mutton were collected aseptically from local vendors of different areas of Hirabad, Latifabad, Phuleli, Qasimabad and Saddar of the Hyderabad city. The Samples were collected randomly in a sterile labelled polythene bags or bijou bottles individually and placed under ice box before transportation. The collected meat samples were brought (at 4 °C within 3-4hours) to the Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam. In the laboratory raw meat sample were processed within 6 hours after collection to avoid contamination and growth of bacteria.

Sample preparation: Each meat sample (10g) were minced individually by using grinder /scissor cut into very fine pieces, then the minced meat were properly mixed and added to (90ml) peptone water by stirring with a stirrer or shaking in vortex mixer. The above specimen were prepared into tenfold dilutions. The dilutions 10^4 , 10^5 and 10^6 were used for further bacteriological investigation. The bacterial counts were expressed as colony forming unit per gram (\log^{10} CFU/g) of meat.

Isolation and Identification of Bacteria: Diluted meat extracts (5 μ l) were streaked over on individual plates of general and selective media for isolation, characterization and quantitative study of bacterial organisms. Culture media that are used in this study

includes Nutrient agar, Nutrient broth, Tryptose agar, Tryptose broth, MacConkey agar, Maconkey broth, Sorbitol MacConkey agar (CM813), Salmonella- Shigella agar, Blood agar, Endo agar base, Hekton enteric agar (CM419) and Xylose - Lysine-deoxychocolate agar (CM469). The identification of isolates was made through cultural, staining and morphological characteristics under microscope with the help of oil immersion objective (100X). Further recognition of the bacterial species were made through different biochemical tests such as oxidase test, catalase test, indole test, coagulase test, methyl red test, Voges Proskauer test, Tripplle Sugar Iron test, urease test and simmon citrate test were performed according to the standards methods recommended by Cruickshank et al., (1973) and Brooks, 2010).

Results: The Prevalence of bacterial species in broiler meat and sheep mutton sold by local vendors of the Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan.

This study was conducted on bacterial contamination of broiler meat and sheep mutton sold by local vendors in Hyderabad. Total of 100 meat samples were obtained from various regions such as Hirabad, Latifabad, Phuleli, Qasimabad and Saddar, the Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan.

The data regarding prevalence of bacterial species in meat samples of broiler and sheep mutton are presented in (Table-1). Among 100 meat samples from different regions of Hyderabad were observed, 25 samples (25%) were found positive for bacterial contamination. It was observed that samples obtained from sheep mutton were recorded as more contaminated 18 (36%) than broiler meat 7 (14%).

Table No-1. The prevalence of bacterial species in broiler meat and sheep mutton sold by local vendors of the Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan.

Meat sample sources	Total No. of samples collected	No. of positive samples	% of positive samples
Broiler	50	7	14
Sheep Mutton	50	18	36

Total bacterial load or viable count in meat samples of broiler meat and sheep mutton

The data regarding bacterial load in meat samples of broiler and sheep mutton obtained from different regions of the Hyderabad are given in (Table 2). In dilution 10^4 , the number of colonies (CFU/ g^{-1}) and mean bacterial counts (g^{-1}) were recorded in the meat

samples of sheep mutton. In (g^{-1}) meat sample of broiler meat, the mean number of 162 colonies were counted for organisms, while in dilution 10^4 the total bacterial counts were recorded as 1.62×10^6 . Similarly the mean number of colonies 125 were recorded in the broiler meat samples with 1.25×10^6 bacterial load.

Table No- 2. The mean bacterial population (bacterial load) in the broiler meat and sheep mutton.

Sources of meat samples obtained	Total no of positive samples	Mean of colonies	Total bacterial count g^{-1}
Broiler	7	162	1.62×10^6
sheep mutton	18	125	1.25×10^6

The occurrence of individual and mixed bacterial species in the samples of broiler meat and sheep mutton.

The broiler meat samples obtained from different regions of the Hyderabad revealed that 7 samples were found positive for bacterial organisms, out of which five samples were contained individual

bacterial species such as Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Salmonella enteritidis. While two samples were contaminated with mixed species with Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus. Whereas in mutton samples, eighteen samples were observed positive for bacterial species, out of which fourteen samples were

contained individual bacterial species such as Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Listeria monocytogenes, Campylobacter jejuni, Bacillus cereus, Salmonella enteritidis and Shigella

dysenteriae. While four samples were contaminated with mixed species Salmonella enteritidis and Shigella dysenteriae.

Table-3. The occurrence of individual and mixed bacterial species contaminate broiler meat and sheep mutton sold by local vendors of the Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

Meat samples source	Total no. of positive samples examined	No Individual samples	No of mixed samples
Broiler	7	5	2
sheep mutton	18	14	4

The overall occurrence of bacterial species in broiler meat sold by local vendors in different regions of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan.

Total of 50 broiler meat samples were collected, 10 from each region of Hirabad, Latifabad, Phuleli, Qasimabad and Saddar. The results regarding the presence of bacterial species in the broiler meat

obtained from various regions of Hyderabad is shown in (Table-4). The investigation revealed that Hirabad 1 (10%) Qasimabad 1(10%), Latifabad 2 (20%) and Phuleli 3 (30%) samples found positive for the different bacterial species. While samples obtained from saddar area did not contain bacterial species. Overall, the higher contamination with the bacterial species were recorded in phuleli region.

Table No-4. The overall occurrence of bacterial species in the samples of broiler meat sold by local vendors in different regions of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan.

S. No.	Name of Area	Total No. of samples examined	Total No. of positive samples	% of positive samples
1	Hirabad	10	1	10
2	Latifabad	10	2	20
3	Phuleli	10	3	30
4	Qasimabad	10	1	10
5	Saddar	10	0	00

The overall occurrence of bacterial species in sheep mutton sold by local vendors in different regions of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

From 50 sheep mutton samples, 10 samples were collected from each region of Hirabad, Latifabad, Phuleli, Qasimabad and Saddar. The results regarding the presence of bacterial species in the sheep mutton obtained from various regions of

Hyderabad is shown in (Table-5). The investigation revealed that Hirabad 3 (30%), Latifabad 5 (50%), Phuleli 6 (60%), Qasimabad 2 (20%) and Saddar 2 (20%) samples were found contaminated with different bacterial species. Overall the higher contamination of the samples was recorded in Phuleli area. While the samples obtained from Qasimabad and Saddar regions showed lower bacterial contamination.

Table No-5. The overall occurrence of bacterial species in sheep mutton sold by local vendors in various regions of Hyderabad.

S. No.	Name of Area	Total No. of samples examined	Total No. of positive samples	% of positive samples
1	Hirabad	10	3	30
2	Latifabad	10	6	50

3	Phuleli	10	5	60
4	Qasimabad	10	2	20
5	Saddar	10	2	20

Incidence of each bacterial species in broiler meat sold by local vendors of Hyderabad.

Incidence of each bacterial species isolated and recognized from broiler meat is presented in (Table-6). Five bacterial species were recognized from broiler meat sold by local sellers of Hyderabad. The bacterial species identified were Escherichia coli (02), Staphylococcus aureus (02), Salmonella enteritidis (01), Shigella dysenteriae (01) and Pseudomonas

aeruginosa (01) and their incidence in meat samples were, 28.5, 28.5, 14.28, 14.28 and 14.28% respectively.

It is concluded from the present investigation that these bacterial species such as Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Salmonella enteritidis, Shigella dysenteriae and Pseudomonas aeruginosa were recognized from broiler meat samples retailed in street vendors of the Hyderabad.

Table No-06. Incidence of each bacterial species in broiler meat samples sold by local vendors of the Hyderabad.

Bacterial species	No of occurring bacterial species in samples	Percentage
Escherichia coli	2	28.5
Staphylococcus aureus	2	28.5
Salmonella enteritidis	1	14.28
Shigella dysenteriae	1	14.28
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	1	14.28

Incidence of each bacterial species in sheep mutton sold by local vendors of Hyderabad.

Incidence of each bacterial species isolated and recognized from sheep mutton are presented in (Table- 07). Seven bacterial species were recognized from mutton retailed by local sellers of Hyderabad.

The bacterial species identified were Escherichia coli (5), Staphylococcus aureus (04), Listeria monocytogenes (03), Salmonella enteritidis (02), Shigella dysenteriae (01), Bacillus cereus (01) and Campylobacter jejuni (01) and their percentage in the samples were: 27.7, 22.2, 16.6, 11.1, 11.1, 5.5 and 5.5% respectively.

Table No-7. Incidence of each bacterial species in sheep mutton samples sold by local vendors of the Hyderabad.

Bacterial species	No of occurring Bacterial species in samples	Percentage
Escherichia coli	5	27.7
Staphylococcus aureus	4	22.2
Listeria monocytogenes	3	16.6
Salmonella enteritidis	2	11.1
Shigella dysenteriae	2	11.1
Campylobacter jejuni	1	5.5
Bacillus cereus	1	5.5

Table No- 8. Biochemical properties of bacterial species isolated from broiler meat and sheep mutton meat.

Bacterial species	Cat	Oxi	Coag	Indol	Ure	M.R	V.P	S.citr	TSI
Escherichia coli	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	A/A
Staphylococcus aureus	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	A/A
Listeria monocytogenes	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve	A/A
Salmonella enteritidis	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	-ve	+ve	A/A
Shigella dysenteriae	+ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	K/A
Campylobacter Jejuni	+ve	+ve	-ve	-	-ve	-	-	+ve	K/K
Bacillus cereus	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	+ve	K/K
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	+ve	+ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve	K/K

Whereas: Oxid = Oxidase K/A=
 -= not tested VP = Alkaline slant and acidic butt
 Voges- Proskauer Ind =
 MR = Methyl red S. citr Indole K/K=
 =Simmons's citrate Alkaline slant and alkaline butt
 Cat = Catalase Ure =
 TSI =Triple sugar iron agar Urease
 Coag =
 Coagulase A/A =
 acidic slant / acidic butt

Table -9. Antibiotic sensitivity against bacterial species isolated from broiler meat and sheep mutton.

Bacterial species	Antibiotic discs used	Inhibitory zone around disc	Sensitivity %	Indication of sensitivity	Degree of sensitivity
Escherichia coli	Ciprofloxacin	12mm	80	++++	Highly sensitive
	Enrofloxacin	11.5mm	76.66	++++	Highly sensitive
	Gentamycin Neomycin	6mm	40	++	Moderate sensitive
	Erythromycin	16mm	46.66	++	Moderate sensitive
	Kanamycin	1mm	6.66	+	Weakly sensitive
	Tetracycline	2mm	13.33	+	Weakly sensitive
	Streptomycin	1.5mm	10	+	Weakly sensitive
	0 mm	0	0	-	Not sensitive
Staphylococcus aureus	Chloramphenicol	12mm	80	++++	Highly sensitive
	Gentamycin	10mm	60	+++	Quite sensitive
	Neomycin	8.5mm	56.33	+++	Quite sensitive
	Erythromycin	8mm	53.33	+++	Quite sensitive
	Sulphamethoxazole	6mm	40	++	Moderate sensitive
	Ciprofloxacin	5mm	33.33	++	moderate sensitive
	Streptomycin	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
Listeria monocytogenes	Erythromycin	15mm	100	++++	Highly sensitive
	Streptomycin	12.5mm	83.33	++++	Highly sensitive
	Gentamycin	12mm	80	++++	Highly sensitive
	Chloramphenicol	10.5	70	++++	Highly sensitive
	Sulphamethoxazole	10.5	70	++++	Highly sensitive
	Tetracycline	10mm	66.66	+++	Quite sensitive

	Penicillin	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
Salmonella enteritidis	Chloramphenicol	14mm	93.33	++++	Highly sensitive
	Sulphamethoxazole	6mm	40	++	Moderate sensitive
	Tetracycline	6mm	40	++	Moderate sensitive
	Kanamycin	2	13.33	+	Weakly sensitive
	Gentamycin	1mm	6.66	-	Weakly sensitive
	Streptomycin	1mm	6.66	-	Weakly sensitive
	Penicillin	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
Shigella dysenteriae	Chloramphenicol	11.5mm	70	++++	Highly sensitive
	Gentamycin	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
	Erythromycin	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
	Sulphamethoxazole	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
	Ciprofloxacin	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive
Campylobacter jejuni	Gentamycin	11.5mm	70	++++	Highly sensitive
	Neomycin	8mm	53.33	+++	Quite sensitive
	Ciprofloxacin	13mm	68.66	+++	Quite sensitive
	Erythromycin	1mm	6.66	-	Weakly sensitive
	Tetracycline	0 mm	0	-	Not sensitive
Bacillus cereus	Enrofloxacin	12mm	76.4	++++	Highly sensitive
	Chloramphenicol	11.5	70	++++	Highly sensitive
	Erythromycin	8mm	53.33	+++	Quite sensitive
	Penicillin	0 mm	0	-	Not sensitive
	Streptomycin	0 mm	0	-	Not sensitive
	Sulphamethoxazole	0 mm	0	-	Not sensitive
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Enrofloxacin	11.5mm	70	++++	Highly sensitive
	chloramphenicol	8mm	53.33	+++	Quite sensitive
	Erythromycin	6.5mm	43.33	+++	Quite sensitive
	Neomycin	6mm	40	++	Moderate sensitive
	Gentamycin	4.5mm	30	++	Moderate sensitive
	Sulphamethoxazole	0mm	0	-	Not sensitive

Efficacy of different drugs against the bacterial species

The various antibiotics were tested against the bacterial species recognized from broiler meat and mutton samples and their efficacy was recorded and presented in Table-9.

Escherichia coli: The results about the antibiogram sensitivity of Escherichia coli investigated during this study are summarized in Table-9. On testing susceptibility to different antibiotics, Escherichia coli

was observed highly sensitive to ciprofloxacin (80%) and enrofloxacin (76.66%). Escherichia coli was found moderate sensitive to neomycin and gentamycin and sensitivity was recorded as 46.66%, 40% respectively. The organism was observed weak sensitive against erythromycin, kanamycin and tetracycline. However the organism showed complete resistance against streptomycin.

Staphylococcus aureus: Staphylococcus aureus was found highly sensitive to chloramphenicol and its susceptibility to drug was recorded as 80%. The

organism showed quite sensitivity against gentamycin, neomycin and erythromycin and their sensitivity was recorded as 60, 56.33 and 53.33 % respectively. The organism was also found moderate sensitive to ciprofloxacin, and sulphamethoxazole. The organism was completely resistant to streptomycin. The results are shown in Table-9.

Listeria monocytogenes: The results about the antibiogram sensitivity of *Listeria monocytogenes* investigated during this study are summarized in Table-9. It is observed that *Listeria monocytogenes* was found highly sensitive to erythromycin (93.33%), streptomycin (83.33%), gentamycin (80%) and chloramphenicol (70%) while quite sensitive to tetracycline (68.42%). *Listeria monocytogenes* was not found sensitive to penicillin.

Salmonella enteritidis: *Salmonella enteritidis* was found highly sensitive to chloramphenicol and their sensitivity against the species recorded as 93.33%. The organism was completely resistant to Penicillin. The organism was weakly sensitive to gentamycin (6.66%), streptomycin (6.66%) and kanamycin (13.33%) respectively. The cells of this species were noted moderate sensitivity to sulphamethoxazole and tetracycline (40%). The results recorded in this study are presented in the Table-9.

Shigella dysenteriae: *Shigella dysenteriae* was determined highly sensitive to chloramphenicol and their sensitivity against the species recorded as 70 %. The organism was found to completely resistant to against the gentamycin, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin and sulphamethoxazole. The results are presented in table-9.

Campylobacter jejuni: *Campylobacter jejuni* was highly sensitive to gentamycin (70%). The organism was quite sensitive to ciprofloxacin (68.66) and neomycin (53.33%). The isolated species was completely resistant to tetracycline. The results are presented in Table-9.

Bacillus cereus: *Bacillus cereus* was found highly sensitive to enrofloxacin and chloramphenicol and their sensitivity against the species was recorded as 76 %, and 70% respectively. *Bacillus cereus* was quite

sensitive to erythromycin (53.33%). While the organism was found completely resistant against penicillin, streptomycin and sulphamethoxazole respectively. The results are presented in Table-9.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa; *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was found highly sensitive to enrofloxacin and its sensitivity was recorded as 70%. The organism was moderately sensitive to neomycin (40%) and gentamycin (30%). Whereas *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was not found sensitive against to sulphamethoxazole. The results are shown in Table-9.

Discussion: Foodborne infections are the widespread and great public health concern of world. In developed and developing countries people are largely affected by foodborne infections. Foodborne diseases are not only affecting the public health but also affecting individual and national economy. Among the food borne microbes of public health concern, most of them are involved in transmission of important zoonotic bacterial pathogen, such agents can cause food spoilage directly or they may affect human health through intake of contaminated foods especially animal origin foods. Food safety and food-borne diseases are important public health hazards around the world. Most of the pathogens resulting in causing food-borne diseases are zoonotic in nature (Busani et al., 2006). Meat borne zoonotic diseases such as Salmonellosis, Campylobacteriosis, Escherichia coli enteritis and food poisoning by Clostridium, Staphylococcus, etc. are the major problems encountered by the consumers eating contaminated meat. *Staphylococcus aureus* is one of the most common agents in bacterial food poisoning outbreaks (Adwan et al., 2005) and symptoms of staphylococcal food intoxication generally occur one to six hours after the food is ingested and the common symptoms are nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, and diarrhea. Salmonellosis (gastroenteritis) is the most common disease in human. Incubation period is generally 6 to 72 hours and can be longer than 10 days (Behraves et al., 2008). Symptoms include nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal cramps and fever of 100 to 102°F (Pickering, 2006). The principal cause of human Campylobacteriosis is mainly *C. jejuni*. *Campylobacter coli* and *C. lari* are

sometimes implicated. The disease conditions associated with infection are either intestinal, presenting as diarrhoea or genital, causing infertility or abortion, cramps, fever, or vomiting; diarrhea may be blood. The majority of Campylobacteriosis results in mild or acute self-limiting gastrointestinal disease. Infrequently complications, such as reactive arthritis and neurological disorders, may occur. Incubation period is usually 2 to 5 days but can be from 1 to 11 days (Allos, 1997). Shigella species are limited to the intestinal tract of humans and cause bacillary dysentery leading to watery or bloody diarrhea. Humans appear to be the only normal host reservoir for Shigella and they become infected by ingestion of contaminated food and water (Arora, 2008). Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an opportunistic pathogen can infect animals and humans. Pseudomonas aeruginosa is the common cause of infections of burn injuries and of the external ear (otitis externa), and is the most frequent colonizer of medical devices such as catheters (Prithviraj et al., 2005). Pseudomonas aeruginosa widely distributed in nature (soil, water, plants, animals). Pseudomonas aeruginosa can grow in distilled water, laboratory hot water baths, hot tubes, wet IV tubing, and other water containing vessels. This explains why the organism is responsible for so many nosocomial infections. Bacillus cereus, one of the most widely distributed microorganisms in nature, has often been found to be responsible for outbreaks of food poisoning and is a common cause of food spoilage (Goepfert et al., 1972; Johnson 1984).

Efficacy of different drugs against the bacterial species isolated from broiler meat and mutton samples.

The different antibiotics were tested against the bacterial isolates identified from broiler meat and mutton samples and their efficacy was recorded and presented in (Table-9).

Escherichia coli: On testing susceptibility to antibiotics, Escherichia coli was found highly sensitive to Ciprofloxacin and enrofloxacin demonstrated during investigation. Escherichia coli was also found quite sensitive to neomycin (46.66%). This result was in close resemblance with those of Sharada et al.(2008) who described

sensitivity of Escherichia coli was highly susceptible to ciprofloxacin, enrofloxacin and chloramphenicol and showed complete resistant to erythromycin.

Staphylococcus aureus: Staphylococcus aureus was found highly sensitive to chloramphenicol and its susceptibility to drugs was recorded as 80%. While the quite effective antibiotics against the organism were erythromycin, gentamycin and Neomycin and their efficacy was recorded as 60, 56.33 and 53.33 % respectively. The findings are closely related to Bala et al. (2016) who described antibiotic susceptibility of Staphylococcus aureus isolated from healthy chickens in poultry farms. Staphylococcus aureus was highly susceptible to chloramphenicol (69.2%). While, the quite effective antibiotics against the organism were erythromycin (45%), gentamycin (60.2%) and neomycin (54.1%).

Listeria monocytogenes: Listeria monocytogenes was found highly susceptible to erythromycin (100%) and streptomycin (83.33%). The organism showed complete resistance against Penicillin. The findings of this study closely resemble with the results of Morobe et al. (2008) who determined antibiogram of Listeria monocytogenes was found that organism was highly susceptible to erythromycin (100%) and streptomycin (80.70%).

Salmonella enteritidis: In this study, the antibiogram pattern of isolated Salmonella enteritidis revealed that the isolates were sensitive against chloramphenicol (93.33%). This result was in close resemblance with those of Akhtar et al. (2010) who described sensitivity of isolates towards chloramphenicol (100%).

Shigella dysenteriae: The isolated Shigella dysenteriae was highly sensitive to chloramphenicol and their sensitivity against the specie recorded as 70%. Shigella dysenteriae was found to completely resistant to against the gentamycin, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin and sulphamethoxazole. The results are in close resemblance with those of Iroha et al. (2010) who determined that isolated species was completely resistant to ciprofloxacin, erythromycin and sulphamethoxazole.

Campylobacter jejuni: On testing susceptibility to antibiotics, *Campylobacter jejuni* was observed highly sensitive to gentamycin demonstrated during this investigation. Whereas the organism was also found quite sensitive to neomycin and ciprofloxacin. The organism was completely resistant to Tetracycline. The results are in close resemblance with those of Toledo et al. (2015) who described *Campylobacter jejuni* was susceptible to ampicillin, erythromycin and gentamycin and was resistant to tetracycline.

Bacillus cereus: The isolated *Bacillus cereus* was found highly sensitive to enrofloxacin and chloramphenicol and their sensitivity against the species was recorded as 76.41 %, and 70% respectively. While the isolated species was resistant to penicillin, & streptomycin. Our findings are partially related to Whong and Kawaja (2007) who reported that *Bacillus cereus* isolates were resistant to penicillin.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa: The results of the antibiotic sensitivity of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* investigated contradict with Shaikh (1999) who reported that sulphamethoxazole was highly sensitive (80%) to the organism. But in this study, the organism found inactive against the sulphamethoxazole.

Conclusion: It is concluded from this study that the broiler meat and sheep mutton samples were found contaminated by various bacterial species such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Bacillus cereus*. Sheep mutton samples were found more contaminated than broiler meat. The higher bacterial load was found in broiler meat samples than sheep mutton samples.

REFERENCES:

Adwan,G., B.A. Shanab, K.Adwan 2005. Enterotoxigenic *Staphylococcus aureus* in raw milk in the North of Palestine.Turk. J. Biol.Vol 29; Pp229-232.

Akhtar, F., I, Khan. A. Hussain and S. U. Rahman 2010. Prevalence and Antibioqram studies of *Salmonella enteritidis* isolated from Human and Poultry sources. Pakistan Vet. J., 30(1): 2528.

Allos. M., 1997 Association between *Campylobacter* infection and Guillain-Barré syndrome, J. Infect. Dis, vol. 2, pp. 125-128.

Arora. D. R.2008. Textbook of Microbiology, CBC Publisher and Distributer, New Delhi, India, 3rd edition.

Bala, H. K., J. C. Igwe, B. O. Olayinka, O. S. Olonitola, J. A. Onaolapo and C. N. Okafo 2016. Antibiotic susceptibility profile of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from healthy chickens in poultry farms in Kano state, Nigeria. Sky. J. of Microbio. Res. Vol. 4(5), pp. 042 - 046.

Behravesh. B 2008. Salmonellosis, in Control of communicable diseases manual, 19th Edition, published by American Public Health Association, pp. 535-540.

Brooks, G.F., Butel, S.J. and Morse, A.S. (2004) Jawetz, Melnick, And Adelberg’s Medical Microbiology. 23rd Edition. McGraw-Hill, Inc., USA. Pp 202-275.

Buriro, R. S., Habib, F., Rind, R., Shah, M. A., Kaleri, R. R., Samoon, A. K., ... & Goswami, N. (2017). Antibiotic sensitivity tests of various micro-organisms from poultry eggs. Pure and Applied Biology (PAB), 6(4), 1417-1426.

Busani, G.Scavia, I. Luzzi, A.Caprioli 2006. Laboratory surveillance for prevention and control of foodborne zoonoses, Ann. Ist Super Sanita, 42; Pp 401-404.

Cruickshank, R., J.P. Dugaid, B.P. Marmion, and R.H.A.Swain 1973. Medical Microbiology 12th ed. Edinburg, Livingstone.

Goepfert, J. M., W. M. Spira, and H. U. Kim. 1972. *Bacillus cereus*: food poisoning organisms. A review. J. Milk Food Technol. 35:213-227.

Iroha I. R., E. C. Ugbo, D. C. Ilang, A. E. Oji and T. E. Ayogu 2010. Bacterial contamination of raw meat sold in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State Nigeria. J. Public Health Epidemio. Vol. 3(2), pp. 49-53.

- Johnson, K. M. 1984. *Bacillus cereus* foodborne illness - An update. *J. Food Prot.* 47:145- 153.
- Kumbhar, M., Kandhro, S., Rind, R., Kaleri, R. R., Chandio, I. S., Farooq, T., ... & Kumar, M. (2018). Prevalence and Incidence of *Staphylococcus aureus* from Wound of Different Animal Species. *Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences*, 14, 12-16.
- Morobe, I. C., Obi, C. L., Nyila, M. A, Gashe, B. A and M. I. Matsheka 2008. Prevalence, antimicrobial resistance profiles of *Listeria monocytogenes* from various foods in Gaborone, Botswana. *Afri. J. of Biotech.* Vol. 8 (22), pp. 6383-6387.
- Pickering, L. K. 2006 .American Academy of Pediatrics, *Salmonella* infections. Red Book, Report of the Committee on Infectious Diseases. pp. 581-584.
- Prithiviraj B, Basis H, Weir T, Suresh B, Najarro E, Dayakar B, Schweizer H, Vivanco J (2005): Down regulation of virulence factors of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by salicylic acid attenuates its virulence on *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* *Infect Immun* 73(9):5319-28.
- Sharada, R. S. Ruban and M. Thiyageeswaran, 2008. Antibiotic resistance pattern of *Escherichia Coli* isolated from poultry in Bangalore. *Int. J. of Microbio.* Vol. 7 No 1. pp 520-525.
- Saleem, F. N. Rani, F. R. Shakoori, M. Aftab, R. Abdullah, M. Iqtedar, A. Kaleem, and S. Nazi 2015. Effect of Gamma irradiation on microbial load of Sheep. *FUUAST J. Bio.*, 5(2): 257-26.
- Shaikh, S. N., 1999. Bacteriological studies on the uteri of slaughtered goats. M.Sc. Thesis. Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Faculty of Animals Husbandry and Veterinary Sciences, Sindh agriculture University, Tando Jam, Pakistan.
- Toledo. Z., R. J. Simaluiza, S. Ochoa and H. Fernández 2015. Occurrence and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli* in Dog feces from Public Parks in Southern Ecuador. *Acta Scie. Vety.* 43: 1284.
- USDA, (2000). Guidelines for slaughter of animals, WHO (2011). <http://www.who.int/zoonoses/vph/en>.
- Whong, C.M.Z and J.K.P. Kwaga 2007. Antibigrams of *Bacillus cereus* isolates from some Nigerian Foods. *Nig Food J*, vol. 25, No. 1, 0189-7241
- Yashoda, K.P., N.M. Sachindra, P.Z. Sakhare, and D.N. Rao 2001. Microbiological quality of broiler chicken carcasses processed hygienically in a small scale poultry processing unit. *J. Food Quality*, 24: 249-259.

